

SOCIAL CARRYING CAPACITY OF HOMESTAY AS A TOOL FOR SUSTENANCE OF COMMUNITY-BASED TOURISM AT RAIMONA NATIONAL PARK, ASSAM, INDIA

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Abstract

Community-based tourism emphasizes getting the local community involved in the community's economic well-being and growth. It aims to empower the residents of tourist locations by promoting tourism activities thereby leading to economic development. The research paper assesses the social carrying capacity of Homestays managed by the communities living in the fringe areas and their sustenance at the newly declared Raimona National Park, Assam. The data was collected randomly through a self-prepared questionnaire covering 100 participants comprising stakeholders of tourism as well as tourists who visited the national park during the period from October to December 2021. Statistical tools such as Chi – Test, One-sample T-test, and Coefficient Correlation were undertaken to analyse the impact of the tourism activities on the community and its social carrying capacity. The research paper explored the customer's satisfaction in the destination and concluded that though they were relatively satisfied with the hospitality of the local community, safety and security, and hygiene, the tourism components like handloom and handicrafts, wellness tourism was relatively limited which can be further explored in a sustained manner to lengthen the duration of stay in the bio - diverse rich destination.

Keywords

Economic Development, Sustenance, Community-based Tourism, Social Carrying capacity, Homestay, Raimona National Park.

1. Introduction

The Raimona National Park lies in the Bodoland Territorial Region of Assam and was declared as a national park on 6th June 2021. It is a deciduous and semi-evergreen forest rich in biodiversity and is popular for its timber treasure of vintage Sal trees (*Shorea Robusta*) and other dominant trees like Arjun (*Terminalia Arjuna*), Simalu (*Bombax ceiba*),

Bhatghilla (*Oroxylum Indicum*), and Bhomora (*Terminalia Balerica*). The park is a large trans-boundary conservation landscape covering a distance of approximately 2400 sq. km and shares its border with the Buxa Tiger reserve of West Bengal and Phibsoo Wildlife Sanctuary of Bhutan. Jomduar happens to be the place where Sir E.P. Gee first spotted and discovered the Golden Langur in 1956 which is endemic in this region and is the mascot of Bodoland Territorial Region. The present Raimona park was a part of the Chirang – Ripu elephant reserve and the park was originally recommended to be named as the Ripu – Chirang Wildlife Sanctuary. The community living in the fringe areas of the tourist destination has four Eco – tourism societies in the different ranges as stated by the President and Secretary of the respective Eco-Tourism Societies of the different ranges namely, the Raimona Haijrai Bangalow Dwimu Eco-Tourism Society, the Raimona Daojeng Gongthong Eco-Tourism society under the Central and the Sanfan range, the Raimona Sona Bhandar Eco-Tourism Development Society and the Raimona Golden Langur Eco-tourism society.

The tourism industry is labor-intensive and is perceived to be a source of alternative economic activity as it adds to local amenities in rural areas where job opportunities are limited. The communities residing in the tourist destinations have an important role to play in promoting tourist products, as it is they who are the main components in forming tourism images. (Pike, 2004). Tosun and Timothy (2003) emphasized that Community based tourism is an important aspect of sustainable tourism development. This approach is more focused on involving local communities to actively participate in the tourism planning and development process. Although conceptually local community participation in tourism is believed to be able to realize the development of sustainable tourism destinations, in practice it is full of challenges and obstacles (Campbell, 1999; Shah and Gupta, 2000; Scheyvens, 2002; Dogra and Gupta, 2012). Lash and Austin (2003) defined Community Based Tourism as “When the local people are involved in all aspects of the conservation and development process both as principal actors and prime beneficiaries”. Community-Based Tourism as the name implies emphasizes getting the local community involved in their economic well-being and growth. It is not simply a tourism activity that aims at maximizing the profits for investors; rather its concern is about the impact on the community and the environmental resources. It is a tool to strengthen the ability of the rural community organization that manages tourism resources with the participation of the local people, homestay being one of its elements. Community-Based Tourism is a branch of Rural Tourism and a niche product where the local community is directly connected to the tourists through tourism activities.

1.1 Carrying Capacity in Tourist Destinations

Every development activity brings about environmental change be it positive or negative and tourism is no exception (Buckley, 2009). Tourism also has the potential to produce something positive for local development but at the same time, its rapid and uncontrollable growth can be a major cause of environmental quality decline as well as loss of local identity and traditional culture (Syamlal, 2008). The environment of the destination is negatively influenced by the increase in tourism (Gossling, 2002; Ramdas and Badaruddin, 2014),

whereas the growth of tourism depends on the quality and characteristics of the environment. As tourism activities become more widespread, there are obvious changes in the environment (Smith, 1989) so the ability to absorb a large number of tourists will present a significant challenge to a tourist location (UNWTO, 1990).

2. Literature Review

The Tourism Area Life Cycle (TALC) proposed by Butler (1980) is one of the most researched and discussed tourism models to investigate the evolution of a tourism destination (Zhang & Xiao, 2014:217; Acharya & Halpenny, 2016:1). The destination undergoes the different stages of the tourism area life cycle just like a consumable product.

According to Manning (2011), social carrying capacity in a destination is associated with innumerable factors such as visitors' motivation, experience, social demographic factors, and so on. Crowding or Mass Tourism according to Ditton et. al, (1983) is perceived on the visitor's expectation of solitude in comparison to those tourists who seek for enhancement of social relationships. The destination should thus be promoted in a manner so that the carrying capacity is not threatened due to depletion of natural or socio–physiological reasons.

Social carrying capacity is also characterized by encounters as stated by Manning and Anderson (2012). If the group size is big, especially in parks, wildlife sanctuaries, or nature trails, it affects the visitor's perception of overcrowding. Saveriades (2000) defines tourism social carrying capacity as the maximum number of tourists that can be present without precluding tourists from enjoying the destination or making the impacts unacceptable by residents. Findings suggest that diverse indicators of social carrying capacity might be considered for tourism destinations (e.g., quality of life, satisfaction, etc.)

Emotions have a dramatic impact on the tourist's decisions as they are direct, intense reactions to an event (Beedie, Terry, & Lane, 2005). Researchers have begun studying its role in tourists' experiences (Gao & Kerstetter, 2018; Lin, Kerstetter, Nawijn, & Mitas, 2014; Nawijn, Mitas, Lin, & Kerstetter, 2013) and found that visitors' thinking and behaviours, and thus leads to a long-term quality life. (Fredrickson & Losada, 2005; Gao, Kerstetter, Mowen, & Hickerson, 2018).

3. Research Question

The paper studies the following research questions:

1. Social Carrying Capacity of Homestay at Raimona and its sustenance.
2. Participation of the community in tourism activities and the level of satisfaction by the tourists.

4. Method

To undertake the study, a self-prepared questionnaire was designed and data were collected randomly from 100 numbers of participants (only domestic tourists). A total of 100 tourists took part in the survey out of which 49 respondents were male and 51 were female. The survey was undertaken from October to December 2021. The Telengana Tour Operators were invited for a familiarization trip by the Tourism Board of Bodoland Council to interact with the local stakeholders and have direct linkages so that there are no economic leakages and the community at large is benefitted. They were a part of this exercise in addition to several wildlife enthusiasts, photographers, and ornithologists. A study was undertaken to perceive the opinion about the safety and security provided in the Homestay along with the amenities on offer and whether they would recommend their friends and colleagues to visit the unexplored destination. Coefficient Correlation, Mean, Chi - Test was undertaken to assess the feelings and comprehension of the value of the stay in the Homestay to cater to the needs of the tourists.

5. Results and Discussion

Table 1.0 shows the number of respondents who undertook the survey. 49% of the respondents were male and 51% of the respondents were female. The total sample size was 100.

Table 1.0 Gender

		Value	Count	Percent
Standard Attributes	Position	1		
	Label	Gender		
	Type	Numeric		
	Format	F1		
	Measurement	Nominal		
	Role	Input		
Valid Values	1	Male	49	49.0%
	2	Female	51	51.0%

Source: Field survey 2021

Table 1.1 Educational Qualification

		Value	Count	Percent
Standard Attributes	Position	3		
	Label	Educational Qualification		
	Type	Numeric		
	Format	F1		
	Measurement	Nominal		
	Role	Input		
Valid Values	1	under graduate	0	0.0%
	2	graduate	36	36.0%
	3	post graduate	41	41.0%
	4	post graduate with diploma	23	23.0%

Source: Field survey 2021

Table 1.1 depicts the educational qualification of the respondents. All the respondents were graduates and above.

Table 1.2 Work Experience

		Value	Count	Percent
Standard Attributes	Position	4		
	Label	Work Experience		
	Type	Numeric		
	Format	F1		
	Measurement	Nominal		
	Role	Input		
Valid Values	1	>1 year	13	13.0%
	2	1-5 years	15	15.0%
	3	5-10 years	10	10.0%
	4	10- 15years	30	30.0%
	5	15-20 years	4	4.0%
	6	<20 years	28	28.0%

Source: Field survey 2021

Table 1.2 shows the Work Experience of the respondents. 30% of the respondents have 10 - 15 years of work experience and 28% have more than 20 years of work experience.

Sustainability includes all components that constitute a complete tourism experience. According to the majority of contributors (Voda et al. 2019; Sharpley 2000; Butler 1991; Vellas and Becherel1999; WCED 1987), the objective of sustainable tourism is to socially, economically, environmentally, and psychologically develop the destination for the continuous positive tourist experience. The development of a destination in a sustained manner has been discussed extensively in order to cater to the needs of tourists, service providers, locals, and whoever is associated with this sector (Eagles et al. 2002). Thus, it has become important to develop a destination under core indicators of sustainability (Sebele 2010; Taylor 1995).

In the table at 2.0 the one-sample t-test regarding the Social carrying capacity at Raimona, the P-value is < 0.001 .

Table: 2.0 One-Sample Test

	Test Value = 50					
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Social Carrying Capacity	-478.891	99	<.001	-48.140	-48.34	-47.94

Source: Field survey 2021

Here, H_0 = Where the sample mean is equal to the population mean and;

H_1 = Where the sample mean is not equal to the population mean.

There is no sufficient evidence to accept the null hypothesis. Since the P-value is below 0.05, it can be concluded that there is no sufficient evidence that the sample mean is the same as the mean of the population. Therefore, we go with the alternate hypothesis in SPSS.

Studies show that tourists are lured to a destination due to the different aspects of sustainability such as environmental, social, economic impacts and benefits derived thereof. (Choi and Murray 2010; Dyer et al. 2007; Ko and Stewart 2002; Nunkoo and Ramkissoon 2011; Oviedo-García et al. 2008; Yoon et al. 2001). Studies have also found that the satisfaction of the stakeholders and the visitors visiting a destination plays a pivotal role for a destination to sustain. (Gursoy et al. 2002; Gursoy, and Kendall 2006; Gursoy and Rutherford 2004; Kaltenborn et al. 2008; Nicholas et al. 2009). Several factors play an important role in the implementation of tourism practices in a sustained manner.

The table at 2.1 shows the correlation between Social Carrying Capacity, Culture, Handicrafts, and Curios and the environmental friendliness (ecological impact) at Raimona.

Table: 2.1 Correlation Coefficient

		Culture, handicrafts and curios	Environmenta lly friendly	Social Carrying Capacity
Culture, handicrafts and curios	Pearson Correlation	1	-.246*	.212*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.013	.034
	N	100	100	100
Environmentally friendly	Pearson Correlation	-.246*	1	.328**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.013		<.001
	N	100	100	100
Social Carrying Capacity	Pearson Correlation	.212*	.328**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.034	<.001	
	N	100	100	100

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field survey 2021

The Output at table 2.1 of Correlation Coefficient between Social Carrying Capacity and Culture, Handloom, and Curios is 0.212. The P-Value of the correlation coefficient is 0.03. As the P-Value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected and it can be concluded that the correlation coefficient between the two variables is positive. Similarly, the output Correlation coefficient between social carrying capacity E and environment is 0.3 28 and the P-value of the correlation coefficient is < 0.001. As the P-value is less than 0.05 the null hypothesis is rejected and it can be concluded that the Correlation Coefficient between the two variables is strongly positive. In the case of Culture, Handloom, and Curios and environmental friendliness, the output between the two variables are - 0.246. The p-value of the Correlation coefficient is 0.013 as the P-value is less than 0.05 null hypotheses is rejected and it can be concluded that the Correlation Coefficient between the two variables is strongly negative.

From the above, it is evident that components Culture, Handloom, and Curios will have to be promoted by the community in a more aggressive manner and they will have to play a proactive role to meet the demand of the visitors.

Table : 2.2 Correlation coefficient

		Cleanliness and Hygiene	Price of destination	Visiting Friends/ Relatives
Cleanliness and Hygiene	Pearson Correlation	1	.579**	.488**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<.001	<.001
	N	100	100	100
Price of destination	Pearson Correlation	.579**	1	.416**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001		<.001
	N	100	100	100
Visiting Friends/ Relatives	Pearson Correlation	.488**	.416**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	
	N	100	100	100

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field survey 2021

The table at 2.2 shows the correlation between the tariff charged, cleanliness, and tourist inflow by visiting friends and relatives at Raimona. From the output of the table illustrated above the correlation coefficient between the variables, cleanliness, and hygiene, and price of destination is 0.579, and visiting friends and relatives is 0.488 respectively. As the P-value of the variables is less than 0.05 the null hypothesis is rejected and it can be concluded that the Correlation Coefficient between the variables is strongly positive.

It is observed from here that the Homestays on offer at the destination are clean and priced as per the visitor's needs.

Table: 3.0 Feelings and comprehension of the value of the tourists' stay at Raimona National Park

Sl. No	Particulars	Agree	Somewhat agree	Disagree	Don't Know
1.	Overall stay in the Homestay was a very good experience	70%	22%	8%	
2.	I have gained good knowledge about the tourist destination and their lifestyle	45%	32%	15%	8%
3.	The homestay was safe and secure	88%	12%		
4.	The homestay was worth every penny paid for.	83%	17%		

Source: Field Data 2020 -21

From table 3.0 it was observed that out of 49 male respondent's 25 percent agreed, 12 percent totally agreed and 12 percent somewhat agreed that their overall stay in the Homestay was a very good experience. Whereas out of 51 female respondents; 33 percent agreed to have had an overall very good experience while staying in the Homestay and 10 percent did not agree to the same. In the case of "Gaining good knowledge about the tourist destination and their lifestyle" 5 percent answered "I don't know, 24 percent agreed to have had gained knowledge, 10 percent somewhat agree and 10 percent did not agree to have had gained enough knowledge about their lifestyle and culture though they stayed in a Homestay in case of male respondents. In the case of the female respondent 3 percent answered "I Don't Know", 21 percent agreed and 22 percent agreed that they had gained some knowledge about the tradition and lifestyle. However, all respondents felt that they should work more on promoting their culture and heritage including the promotion of handloom and handicrafts.

From the survey undertaken it was observed that a considerable number of respondents preferred to stay in star category hotels with the provision to rest and relax and rejuvenate though they were satisfied with their stay in the homestay. The food offered to the respondents was mostly local cuisine but some of the respondents were of the opinion that since the culture and cuisine differ to a great extent from the community of the destination, few regular Indian dishes should also be introduced for a variety in the cuisine on offer. Thus, it necessitated the presence of hotels so that the tourists could have a taste of different flavours that are available in a hotel. The road connectivity to the destination was excellent and beyond the expectation of the respondents. As the respondents categorically opined of improvement in experiential activities in handloom and textile with the provision of curios, heritage, and culture of the destination; for the life cycle growth of the destination, it is pertinent for the government in the Council, State Tourism Department, and the department in the centre to take appropriate steps as soon as possible to make the destination a tourist hotspot like that of Manas National Park or Kaziranga National park which are both UNESCO heritage sites located in Assam, India.

6. Conclusion and Recommendation

Visitation of natural attractions is an important element of travel and the desire to visit an unexplored destination with an intact environment has become a trend. Hence it is vital to safeguard the environment for the tourism industry keeping in mind the customer's satisfaction. It is crucial to evaluate the public resources used by the tourism industry and the estimation of the total willingness to pay for the resources that implies an important criterion for the development of the destination life cycle product, estimating its effects and determining the optimal steps of action. For estimation, the specific tourist site has to be determined along with the country of residence of the tourists and the total population of the destination. If the carrying capacity of the resources has a direct impact on the total usage levels, the observed values might reflect on the true value of the site. The effects of congestion on the tourist sites are then measured.

1. The destination has gradually evolved as a National Park and so the local community is highly satisfied with regard to their engagement in the ancillary activities besides cultivation as it has led to an additional income to the community.
2. The local community living in the fringe area of the national park has concentrated on the development of Home Stays and ownership of Jeep for a safari inside the national park. They can also improvise on setting up looms in their homestays which becomes an additional attraction to the tourists. Curio's too can be promoted which will add to the household income and provide employment to the womenfolk in the villages leading to self-sufficiency.
3. The destination should be developed in a sustainable manner and the government bodies have to play an important role in its development by implementing visionary policies.
4. The economic leakages in the destination should be minimal and the societies formed in the destinations in the four ranges must have equitable economic distribution.
5. The Wellness tourism activities can perhaps be easily promoted to the tourists more aggressively through proper "Cowmunication"; a new trend of cow cuddling that has started in the western countries as a part of rejuvenation as shared by Shri Valmiki Hari Krishna of Valmiki Tours and chairman of the Federation of Telangana Chambers of Commerce and Industry due to the rural settings of the destination.
6. The community living in the fringe areas will have to collaborate with the Forest Department and the Tourism department of the Council of Bodoland to impart awareness on guide training regarding "Botanical Tours" for its rich biodiversity.

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